

Influence of Labor Management Relationship on Employee's Performance

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ABSTRACT: This article theoretically examined the effect of employment relations on employees in multinational corporations with a special focus on Dangote Cement. The article observed that labour-management relations also known as industrial relations play an imperative role in improving and sustaining employees' performance. It serves as the nerves of industrial harmony. The target population of this study, which is finite (being defined), is the total number of Dangote Cement Plant in Ibese, Ogun State, Nigeria. The population comprises staff whose population is two hundred and sixty (260). The use of a questionnaire was adopted to elicit information from the cross-section of the selected population. The correlation coefficient value ranges from 0 – 1 and has an acceptable value of 0.88, which indicates higher reliability of the measurement instrument and low error variance, implying that the instrument is reliable. While the analysis was done using regression analysis. The findings revealed that there is a significant influence of employee's participation, trade union, and industrial harmony on employee performance. Organizations should encourage mutual relationships among employees, as well as provide conducive working conditions/ environment for employees, like organizational learning, effective communication among employees, which will enhance their productivity and employee's performance.

KEYWORDS: employee's performance, productivity,

INTRODUCTION

Labour-management relations also known as industrial relations play an imperative role in improving and sustaining employees' performance. It serves as the nerves of industrial harmony. Labour-management relations usually began with the emergence of trade unionism following the industrial revolution. This was when the large-scale production system began. In the face of irregularities in human behaviour, there was a need to effectively harness human effort towards the optimum productive capability in the workplace. This is the relationship between the worker and his organization.

There are two categories of groups that exist in an organization namely; labour and management. These groups formed the pilot upon which major organization actions or activities revolve. Labour is made up of groups of individuals that come from different backgrounds with different ideologies. Thapliyal (2019) Management, on the other hand, forms the policies that help in integrating and reducing the conflicting ideologies of labourers.

According to Hassan (2016), the process of combining resources and tasks to meet stated organizational goals is known as management. Allan Flanders posits that 'the system of labour-management relation may therefore be described as the study of institutional rule; and as a result, labour-management relations can be regarded as a study of job-regulation institutions. Budd (2018) on his part described labour management relation as the entirety of human interaction at work that is based on and arises from employment.

According to Dunlop An industrial relations system is defined as "a set of actors, circumstances, and an ideology that links the system together, as well as a set of rules, developed to regulate the players at the workplace and in the work community" at any point in its growth. It refers to the regulation of employment relationships by all parties, labour, employer/management and the state involved in the attainment and sustenance of increased productivity, industrial harmony, and development of the workplace parties.

The laws and policies that govern and organize employment, as well as how they are formed and implemented, and how they affect the demands and interests of employees and employers, are referred to as labor management relations (LMR).Crane (2016)

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The labor-management relationship is an organizational justice framework that incorporates organizational culture and management style, as well as grievance and conflict resolution regulations and procedural sequences.

Indeed, the goal of the labour-management interaction is to establish harmonious employee relations and reduce workplace friction. Budd (2018). The labour-management relationship has ramifications for both work organization and economic policy. (Sridharan.2017). From the development and operation of national and local institutions (Trade Unions) and collective bargaining, the focus has increasingly shifted to strategic human resource policy. (Sridharan.2017).

In terms of definitions, trade unions can be created from a variety of angles. Ayewoh, (2019) a trade union is described as a continuous association of wage earners who complement one another as autonomous producers, but who rely on employees to increase their bargaining power with employers. A trade union, according to Khan (2018), is an organization of employees founded to enhance and safeguard the terms and conditions of their members' employment, including their living standards.

Kenee, (2014) defines a trade union as 'any combination of workers or employers whether temporarily or permanently, the purpose of which is to regulate the terms and conditions of employment of workers, whether the combination in question would or would not apart from this Decree, be unlawful because of any of its purpose being in restraint of trade, and whether its purposes do not include the provision of benefits for its workers All of the definitions above clearly show that a trade union is any group of wage earners, whether temporary or permanent, whose primary goal is to regulate the relationship between workers and management in an organization, impose restrictive conditions in the conduct of business, and provide benefits to their members. Collective bargaining on the other hand is the process by which organized groups of employees and employers search for ways to coordinate their conflicting goals through common circumstances (Vettori 2015).

According to David (2016), collective bargaining is "the process of deciding working conditions and terms of employment through negotiation between an employer, a group of employers, or one or more representatives of a worker organization in order to reach an agreement" It is, in essence, a rule-making procedure.

As it can see from the many definitions, collective bargaining affects both management and pay relations, and as a result, it is critical to the development of industrial relations. In the absence of these, we might argue that the law requires both management and labor to negotiate salary, hours, and other employment terms and conditions in good faith. It is primary responsibility is to organize employment terms and conditions in a way that benefits everyone (Bamber and Sheldom 2015).

Statement of the Problem

The workplace's industrial interaction between management and employees is critical to the organization's performance. When employees are free of grievances and are pleased at work, productivity rises because employees always put forth their best effort. Unfortunately, based on observations, some management appears to be unaware of this truth. They don't appear to provide employees a chance to engage in organizational decision-making, which frequently leads to conflict.

Existing literature has shown that there is a significant relationship between employee participation in decision-making and employees' performance within an organization. However, qualitative analysis is frequently used in this literature. As a result, this study will be conducted using a quantitative data analysis method. Labour relations experts have claimed that 'unions are the fault of poor labour management relation'. Management is relatively free to operate as it pleases without a union, but with one, the direction of the workforce is controlled by the term of a contract. The manager is therefore faced with the task of ensuring that all employees are treated fairly, directing their efforts toward the organization's goals, and promoting a cordial relationship between employer representatives (union) and management.

Trade unions have been shown in the literature to be critical in boosting employee performance in a firm by ensuring favourable terms and conditions of employment. However, the researchers often make use of qualitative analysis and public enterprise as a case study. Hence, this work will adopt a quantitative method of data analysis to carry out its study using a private company as its case study.

Another important factor that affects employee performance in a company is industrial harmony.

Non-recognition of worker social expectations, as well as challenges from workers or unions seeking increased participation in management decision-making, exacerbate the problem. The incident depicted above exemplifies the strained relationship between management and employees. The previous study has indicated that maintaining and boosting employee performance in an organization requires industrial harmony. However, qualitative analysis is frequently used in studies. For the aim of this project, a quantitative method of data analysis will be used.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to ascertain the influence of the labour-management relationship on employee performance. However, the specific objectives are outlined below:

1. To evaluate how employee participation in decision-making affects their performance.

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2. To evaluate the effect of the trade union on employees' performance.
3. To evaluate how industrial harmony affects employee performance in an organization.

Research Question

1. To what extent does employee participation in decision-making affect performance?
2. To what extent does trade (labour) union affect employee performance?
3. To what extent does industrial harmony affect employee performance in an organization?

Research Hypotheses

Ho: There is no significant relationship between employee participation in decision-making and employees' performance.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the trade union and employee performance.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between industrial harmony and employees' performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Labour-management Relations and Organization Performance

Since its inception in the twentieth century, the idea of labour relations has received scholarly definitions.

Labour-management Relationships (LMR) is concerned with building an enabling work environment for stronger interpersonal relationships in the organization, with a focus on achieving the organization's goals and objectives. The study of the interaction between employees and employers in an organization is known as LMR. Joel Chukwuyem is a Nigerian musician (2020) Effective employee relations, in general, place a high value on an organization's employees, resulting in increased employee motivation, engagement, and performance.

LMR, according to Yogcai (2015), is a specific area in human resource management, and LMR, according to Jing (2019), is an organization's determined effort to govern the relationship between employee and employer toward the fulfillment of the organization's goals.

In an organization, effective LMR boosts employee confidence, trust, and loyalty. Through open communication, a frequent feedback system, a joint decision-making workers union, and transfer of responsibility to staff, the employer earns trust and loyalty. Onyemaechi Joseph (2014). The incapacity of an employer to instil trust and respect in their personnel will have a detrimental impact on the organization's success. Positive ties between management and labour have been found to improve employee and organizational performance, according to theories. The effectiveness of the relationship between managers and employees has a favourable impact on organizational performance. Joel Chukwuyem is a Nigerian musician (2020).As a result, he emphasized the need for managers to maintain appropriate communication with their personnel. Every human being has a natural want to be respected, valued, and acknowledged for their traits and abilities, as well as to have the freedom or control over how they carry out their responsibilities. Managers will treat employees with contempt if a corporation is unable to recognize these features of human nature. Employees become demotivated as a result of these actions. Positive human interactions between bosses and employees have long been regarded as vital to company success.

Labor Participation in Decision Making and Organizational Performance

Participatory decision-making (PDM), also known as employee decision-making participation, is focused with shared decision-making in the workplace. Mitchell (2017).Employee participation in decision-making has been identified as a management strategy for enhancing organizational performance by pursuing shared goals between employees and employers. Allowing employees to participate in the drafting of the mission statement, the establishment of policies and processes, and the determination of wage, promotion, and incentives accomplishes this.

Employees can now directly or indirectly participate through labour participation in decision-making. James is a man of many talents (2018) Consider employee participation in decision-making as a form of social justice, allowing workers to have a say, if only on topics that impact them.

Knowing that he was involved in the decision-making process motivates an employee to work harder to reach a goal; involvement not only boosts an employee's contribution to problem analysis but also improves their ability to make critical operational decisions (Yogcai, 2015). Individuals are allowed to take on job responsibilities and participate in joint decision-making for the firm's overall well-being through Employee Participation. Management Study Guide (2016).

Employee decision-making participation is a type of delegation in which the subordinate gains more authority and freedom of choice in terms of bridging the communication gap between management and employees. Noah's Ark (2017).Employee involvement might be great or minimal in a company. All types of employees are included in the planning process, which is referred

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to as a high degree of involvement (deep employee involvement in decision making). A low level of involvement (shallow employee involvement in decision-making) on the other hand, implies a very exclusive planning process involving only senior management. Noah's Ark (2017). A high level of employee involvement in decision-making allows frontline staff to have a say in the planning process.

These are the people who are closest to the client and can help new products and services stand out, which is an important part of the entrepreneurial process. Li (2016). This means that involving employees in the planning process for prospective innovations may help the organization recognize opportunities more quickly. Zivkovic is a Serbian politician (2019). People who feel that the upper echelon is responsible for organizational achievements frequently overlook the power and contributions of those at lower levels. Woodworth is a character in the film Woodworth (2016). As a result, the necessity of employee participation in decision-making is overlooked.

Trade Union and Organizational Performance

Trade unions are worker-run organizations that fight for their members' rights and campaign for better working conditions for their members. Members of the same or comparable trades gather together as a unified unit to fight for a shared aim, as Buchmueller and Di Nardo (2014) perceive it. The trade union is generally made up of employees whose main purpose is to bargain for better working conditions. A trade union is also a group of workers who band together to increase their bargaining power with their counterparts TUC-RLF (2012). The current unfavorable master-servant relationship between employers and employees forced the development of trade unions. Workers who are paid slave wages' are also a concern. (Baah,2000)

A trade union, also known as a labour union, is a group of workers or employees who have banded together to pursue similar objectives such as improving working conditions and defending and promoting their common interests through collective action. A trade union bargains with the employer or management on behalf of its members and negotiates labour contracts through its leadership. Row (2010). A trade union is a group of employees formed to bargain with employers through management. Wörden (2009) Trade unions are employee-run organizations whose principal goal is to represent employees' interests to employers. Taylor and Armstrong (2014).Trade unions can have a positive impact on an organization's performance by successfully negotiating.

Furthermore, trade unions can have a detrimental impact on the functioning of a firm by causing employees to cease working or engage in sabotage. Unionized organizations are more productive than nonunionized organizations, according to Amah and Ahiauzu (2013).Organizational performance can be improved through trade unions. Wörden (2009) & Cote (2013).

However, when trade unions fail to peacefully negotiate for better conditions, organizational performance suffers. Trade unions frequently engage in strikes during which organizational performance suffers.Cote (2013).A trade union is an ongoing association of employees created for the goal of securing a variety of benefits.Podr (2011). They represent their members when they have work-related issues, negotiate for wages, working hours, holidays, changes in working practices, and employees facing layoffs, retrenchment, promotion, or transfer. Most trade unions also provide training to their members on topics such as employment rights, health and safety, and other topics.

Industrial Harmony and Organizational Performance

Industrial harmony refers to a cordial and cooperative agreement between employers and employees on working relationships for the mutual benefit of both parties. Laden (2017). Industrial harmony is concerned with the connection between management and employees in terms of employment terms and conditions, as well as the work environment Puttapalli and Vuram (2017).

It is, after all, a situation in which employees and management freely collaborate to achieve the organization's aims and objectives. Industrial harmony means "attempting to find solutions between conflicting objectives and values; between the profit motive and social gain; between discipline and freedom, between authority and industrial democracy; between bargaining and co-operation; and between conflicting interests of the individual, group, and organization," according to Lester.

Industrial harmony is made up of two words: industrial and harmony. Any productive activity in which a single person or a group of people is (are) involved is referred to as industrial harmony refers to the peaceful coexistence of employees and management in the workplace, which emerges directly or indirectly from the union-employer relationship. At all levels, the ties that exist within and outside of organizations are formed to advance their particular interests. Industrial harmony also includes the mechanisms through which these relationships are expressed (for example, collective bargaining, worker engagement in decision-making, and grievance and dispute resolution), as well as the handling of the conflict between employers and employees when it develops.

Individuals are part of a social structure that is extroverted but self-contained. Individuals' behavior, activities, and roles are shaped by organizational or societal cultures; the value system and other organizational factors impact the process and determine the outcome or response of individuals. The industrial relations system, according to Dunlop, consists of a set of actors, settings,

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and ideology that connects them all, as well as a set of laws that regulate the actors in the company. Managers, workers, and representatives are the actors in the systems.

The role of employers in improving organizational industrial harmony has gotten a lot of attention in the industrial relations literature. This is because many Nigerian businesses are beset by a slew of industrial issues brought on by inefficient and unproductive management styles, as well as strained ties between management and labor unions like Osamwonyi and Ugiagbe (2015). As a result, most businesses' output has been impaired as a result of frequent industrial disputes. A healthy and cooperative working relationship between employers and employees is referred to as industrial harmony.

Theoretical Framework Labor management relation has been studied by various researchers and has been in existence for a very long time. However, there is no universally fixed theory on labor management relation, Therefore, this study will theoretically view labor management relations from unitary theory, Pluralist theory, Marxist theory and the System theory

Unitary Theory

The unitary theory is based on the idea that there is only one source of authority, which is management. The role of organizational leaders is to foster employee loyalty and dedication Farnham, (2020). Organizations are viewed as a collection of teams that collaborate to achieve common goals, with no conflicts of interest between managers and employees. The unitary theory holds that employers and employees may work together for common goals, interests, and values, and that management should lead by example to achieve organizational goals. Trade unions are considered as a source of industrial dispute and hence are not required for peaceful conflict resolution. As a result, conflicts in the workplace are viewed as dysfunctional, often leading to disloyalty, and so jeopardizing the organization's well-being. Cooper and his colleagues (2015). The state is viewed as a key player in the development of LMR systems.

The unitary theory's main strength is that it seeks to unify employer and employee interests to improve employee commitment and loyalty. Peccei and Guest (2015). Employees are viewed as significant stakeholders in the organization, and their well-being is carefully regarded in maintaining the organization's welfare. Unitary theory can be utilized as a foundation for stakeholder management.

Ackers and Payne (2018). The unitary theory also emphasizes managers' involvement in achieving win-win circumstances (variable-sum situations) for people and organizations, in which their interests are correctly aligned. Managers are expected to stress their leadership talents in addition to their managerial ways of managing employee interactions. Payne and Ackers (2018). There will be no great demand for trade unions if they can be compelling and influential leaders in the organization.

When governments formulate policies on taxation, interest rates, and inflation, they should consider the impact these policies would have on employees. The unitary hypothesis believes that all stakeholders are sensible individuals who will look for common ground.

This idea gives a consistent reason for emphasizing common goals to build a stable labor-management Relations system. In terms of industrial relations, the unitary theory is essentially individualist. Many LMR systems around the world have moved away from collectivist (union-led) LMR paradigms and toward individualist paradigms. As an example, as the primary tool of monetary policy, the central bank can lend money to financial firms to affect their interest rates. Because banks borrow money from the central bank and then lend it out at a higher rate to make the majority of their profit, central bank interest rates are usually lower than commercial interest rates. The government institution can influence interest rates for everyone who wants to borrow money for economic investment by changing interest rates.

Changes in interest rates and total output can cause quick changes in investment. Because there is no conflict of interest between the participants in an LMR system, the unitary theory assumes that there is a high level of harmony inside an enterprise.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

This part reviewed literature from previous studies. These are the combination of previous studies that have established the relationship between Trade Union, industrial harmony and joint decision making and what effect they have on employee's performance.

There are commonalities of thought as to the effects of Trade Union, industrial harmony and joint decision on employees performance. Industrial harmony is concerned with the relationship between management and employees concerning the terms and conditions of employment and the workplace. In effect, it is a situation where employees and management cooperate willingly in pursuit of the organization's aims and objectives Puttapalli and Vuram (2017).

Increased employee performance necessitates industrial peace and harmony, which can only be achieved through good labor-management relations. Both management and employees must recognize that they play critical roles in the organization, and they must regard one another as essential to the achievement of the organization's goals and objectives. This can be accomplished by

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viewing and treating the organization as a system. In her study of the "impact of labor-management relations on employees' performance in a firm," Onwu Nonyelum Felicia (2012)

It is well known that workers will work harder to achieve a goal if they are involved in the decision-making process, management should allow workers to participate in decision-making. If workers are allowed to participate in decision-making, they will feel privileged and obligated to work hard to achieve the joint goal. When a grievance or disagreement arises in the workplace, management should endeavor to resolve it as soon as possible, either through negotiation or collective bargaining, before it becomes too late and a strike occurs. Management, on the other hand, should acknowledge the presence of labor unions.'

Management of Labor Workers' performance is influenced by their relationship. It is the responsibility of management to ensure that a friendly connection is maintained. Both parties must set the terms and conditions under which employees will work through collective bargaining, and if both parties fulfill their responsibilities, there will be harmonious coexistence. Workers should be given the opportunity to participate in decision-making in order to give them a sense of belonging and to improve their performance. Because employees spend the majority of their time working for the company, their opinions should be sorted before choices are made. Okere, & Ezeanyej, (2014)

Employees must be motivated in order for management and employees to work in harmony and to improve performance. To avoid unnecessary sabotage and to enable them to speak with one voice, the communication gap between management and workers must be addressed. Sanyal, Hisam, and BaOma(2018) study support these scholars' viewpoints.

To attain proper labour management relations that influence employees' performance strategies such as the survey feedback, team building, managerial grid, sensitivity training, workplace training and adequate compensation must be given maximum attention. Onwe (2014). However, this study will use an unquoted company as its case study.

METHODOLOGY

The target population of this study, which is finite (being defined), is the total number of Dangote Cement Plant in Ibese, Ogun State, Nigeria. However, due to time budgetary constraints (finances), geographical location and subject area of interest, the study is limited to Ibese, Ogun State which constitutes the sampling unit from where employees who are readily accessible for this study were selected to form the sample. The population comprises staff whose population is two hundred and sixty (260). The use of a questionnaire was adopted to elicit information from the cross-section of the selected population. The correlation coefficient value ranges from 0 – 1 and has an acceptable value of 0.88, which indicate higher reliability of the measurement instrument and low error variance, implying that the instrument is reliable. While the analysis was done using regression analysis.

1. Data Presentation and Analysis

A sum of 260 copies of the questionnaire was circulated and out of the 260 questionnaires handed out, 11 of the questionnaire were invalid because they were not properly answered which was 4.2% of the allotted questionnaire furthermore, 29 representing 11.1% were not answered after they were collected from the respondents and 220 of the questionnaire were valid for the analysis which was 84.7% of the allotted questionnaire as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

		Frequency	Per cent
Gender	Male	91	41.4
	Female	129	58.6
	Total	220	100.0
Age	21-30	70	31.8
	31-40	131	59.5
	41-50	8	3.6
	51 and above	11	5.0
	Total	220	100.0
Marital status	Single	115	52.3
	Married	105	47.7
	Total	220	100.0
Educational Qualification	OND/NCE	3	1.4
	B.SC/HND	72	32.7
	M.Sc./MBA	93	42.3
	PHD	52	23.6
	Total	220	100.0

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Number of years spent in the current organization	less than 5 years	85	38.6
	5-10 years	128	58.2
	11-15 years	7	3.2
	Total	220	100.0
Employment status	Full time	120	54,5
	Contract staff	100	45.5
	Total	220	100.0

(Source: Field 2020)

Test of Hypotheses

Regression was used to measure the effect and the relationship of the independent variable and the dependent variable of the different hypotheses.

H0: Employee participation in decision making, trade union, and industrial harmony does not affect employees' performance.

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.256 ^a	.065	.061	.83132	
ANOVA					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	10.543	1	10.543	15.256	.000 ^b
Residual	150.657	218	.691		
Total	161.200	219			
Coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	2.490	.340		7.324	.000
EMPLOYEES PARTICIPATION	.331	.085	.256	3.906	.000
TRADE UNION	.103	.104	.366	5.799	.000
INDUSTRIAL HARMONY	.409	.089	.296	4.576	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Performance					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Labour participation					

The table presents the results that revealed the degree to which the variance in employees performance is explained by trade union and industrial harmony. This is represented by R square which equals .065 and expressed is 6.5%. This shows that industrial harmony and trade unions only account for 6.5% of employees' performance, while the standard error estimate is .83132 which signifies an error term.

DECISION RULE AND INTERPRETATION

Null hypothesis should be rejected when the significance value is below 0.05. The ANOVA table shows that the F value is 15.256 at .000^b Significance level. The implication is that that employees participation ($\beta = .331$; $t=3.906$; $p<0.000$), trade

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union ($\beta = .103$; $t = 5.799$; $p < 0.000$) and industrial harmony ($\beta = .409$; $t = 4.576$; $p < 0.000$), have significant influence on employees' performance.

Decision: The Null hypothesis is therefore rejected because the significance is below 0.05. Therefore, there is a significant influence of employees participation, trade union and industrial harmony on employees' performance.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first hypothesis tested was: employees participation has a significant effect on employee performance. Using regression analysis, the result derived showed that there is a relationship between employees participation and employees' performance. This means that the employees understand the fact that there are sometimes that the organization needs to turn a blind eye to certain situations and the result shows that despite this the employees are still committed to their duties to the organization. This repudiates what (Jehn, 1995) said.

The second hypothesis tested was: trade union has a significant role in job effectiveness. Using regression analysis, the result derived showed that there is an effect of competitive grievance management strategy on job effectiveness. There are times in which the organization needs to make an urgent decision concerning the affairs or the structures of the organization and a delay in such decisions could lead to serious devastation.

The third hypothesis tested was: Industrial harmony has a significant effect on employees' efficiency. Using regression analysis, the result derived showed that industrial harmony influences employees' efficiency. The employees should be motivated for harmony to reign between management and, to enhance performance. The communication gap between the management and workers must be bridged to prevent unnecessary sabotage and enable them to speak with one voice, thereby avoiding rumour-mongering. These researchers view is further validated by the findings of Dr Pedro Brito and Pedro Galin (2017).

RECOMMENDATIONS

By studying the findings and the conclusions that have been stated above, it can be resolved that the objectives of the research have been reached and the following recommendations which can not only be applied in the manufacturing sector but other sectors include:

1. Organizations should encourage mutual relationships among employees, as well as provide conducive working conditions/environments for employees, like organizational learning, effective communication among employees, which will enhance their productivity and organizational performance. Different strategies of managing grievance ought to be educated by the management of the universities so that notwithstanding when they don't think about the contention like a relational struggle, the general population included will pick the best approach.
2. The individuals involved in grievance ought to be liberal and prepared to hear out the other individual to take the most ideal and sane choice while managing grievance. Employees should be educated that grievance is not a bad occurrence and also should be educated about the five strategies of managing grievance and also the strengths and weaknesses associated with each strategy. Organizations should emphasize team building and create an environment that encourages respect and equality among employees. Finally, organizations should inhabit the culture of involving the employee's in the decision-making process and also every employee should be given the privilege of expressing themselves.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Research is an unavoidable boundless circle and data is dynamic and broad, accordingly, there will be further investigations on this theme. The discoveries of this research supplement past investigations in demonstrating proposals for approaching studies which are rearranged underneath;

1. There should be more studies carried out in Nigeria because most studies were carried out in Kenya and Jordan. Seeing the littleness of the example measure expanded research with a bigger example estimate incorporating impersonation in different areas with higher population would improve the legitimacy of the exploration and own speculation and clearing expressions increasingly appropriate. Other researchers could endeavour to make use of a mixed-method that is a quantitative and qualitative research method
2. The conclusion drawn from this research work is limited due to the restricted sample size of employees; subsequent studies may therefore be embarked upon to explore the subject of the influence of labour management relationship on employees' performance. Also, this research was carried out in Ibesse, Ogun State,

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another research could be made in other states/regions of Nigeria. Furthermore, the influence of the labour-management relationship could be studied in the manufacturing industry

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